

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART IV. OXIDATION WITH POTASSIUM CHLORATE.

BY BALWANT SINGH AND SOHAN SINGH.

Potassium iodide, ferrous ammonium sulphate, thalious chloride, arsenious oxide and potassium antimonyl tartrate were titrated potentiometrically against standard potassium chlorate in presence of a large excess of hydrochloric acid. With the addition of potassium chlorate, E.M.F. was found to rise steadily except in arsenious oxide where it did not change but near the equivalence point. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential followed by a steady rise in each case.

Potassium bromate and potassium iodate, especially the latter, have been extensively used as reagents in quantitative analysis. Practically no work has been done with potassium chlorate as a volumetric reagent in oxidation-reduction reactions.

An aqueous solution of potassium chlorate is fairly stable and reacts slowly with dilute hydrochloric acid with the evolution of chlorine. Raising the temperature, increases the rate of evolution of the gas; and the reaction is accelerated with platinum as catalytic agent.

In the present investigation potassium iodide, ferrous, thalious, arsenious and antimonious compounds have been determined potentiometrically by titrating them against standard potassium chlorate in presence of a large excess of hydrochloric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The oxidation-reduction electrode, which consisted of a bright platinum foil, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The cell was placed in a water-bath, temperature of which was kept at 25°.

A known weight of each salt was weighed into a titration vessel and the required amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid added to keep its concentration above 5 *N*. Standard potassium chlorate was added from a burette, the mixture stirred by a mechanical stirrer and the progress of oxidation followed with the potentiometer.

Potassium iodide and ferrous ammonium sulphate were titrated in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide to prevent oxidation by the atmospheric air. Iodine monochloride has been used as a catalyst in the case of

thallous chloride and arsenious oxide. In the case of potassium iodide, the temperature of the bath was 10°. In the case of potassium antimonyl tartrate, the temperature of the bath was kept at 45°, as the reaction was very slow at 25°.

A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration, as typical of that set, is recorded in the following table.

TABLE I.

0.6086 G. of potassium iodide dissolved in 10 c.c. of water, and 50 c.c. of conc. hydrochloric acid titrated against *M*/20-potassium chlorate.

KClO ₃ , 7.000 c.c.	E.M.F. 0.250 volt	<i>E</i> / <i>C</i> .	KClO ₃ , 24.200	E.M.F. 0.634 volt	<i>E</i> / <i>C</i> .
10.000	0.302	17 m. volt/c.c.	24.300	0.646	120 m. volt/c
11.000	0.321	19	24.350	0.654	160
12.000	0.404	83	24.375	0.662	320
13.000	0.506	102	24.400	0.678	640
14.000	0.526	20	24.425	0.814	5440 (maximum) 640
16.000	0.546	10	24.450	0.830	200
20.000	0.570	6	24.500	0.840	160
22.000	0.585	7	24.600	0.856	100
23.000	0.598	13	24.800	0.876	28
23.600	0.610	20	25.300	0.890	8
24.000	0.620	25	26.300	0.898	
		70			

The titrations, one for each substance, are represented by the curves given in page 29.

D I S C U S S I O N .

In these titrations, with the addition of the standard potassium chlorate solution, the E.M.F. rose steadily except in arsenious oxide, where it did not change but near the equivalence point. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential, followed by a steady rise in each case.

In the case of potassium iodide, another break in the E.M.F. was observed when nearly half of the volume of the titrant required for the equivalence point was added to the reaction mixture.

The reaction between potassium iodide and potassium chlorate in the presence of a large excess of hydrochloric acid takes place in two stages as follows

The completion of each of these stages is marked by a break in the E.M.F. The first break takes place when all the iodide is converted into iodine and the second break corresponding to the equivalence point, is observed when all the iodine, liberated during the first stage, is changed to iodine monochloride.

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to potassium iodide, ferrous am. sulphate, thallous chloride, arsenious oxide, pot. antimonyl tartrate.

From the volume of potassium chlorate required in each titration, corresponding to the equivalence point, the amount of the compound was calculated. In the following table the values obtained are compared with the amount of the substance taken.

TABLE II.

Potassium iodide. (taken).	(found).	Ferrous Am. sulphate (taken).	(found).	Thallous chloride. (taken).	(found).	Arsenious oxide (taken).	(found).	antim. tartrate (taken).	(found).
0.6086g.	0.6080 g.	1.7394 g.	1.7388 g.	1.0780	1.0778	0.4452	0.4441	1.5102	1.5096
0.4950	0.4945	0.9675	0.9670	0.7018	0.7015	0.2445	0.2438	0.9123	0.9121
0.3595	0.3593	0.5780	0.5775	0.4854	0.4848	0.2226	0.2221	0.5672	0.5671
0.2002	0.1998	0.4571	0.4567	0.2850	0.2844	0.1335	0.1333	0.3196	0.3196
0.1660	0.1656			0.1798	0.1794	0.0890	0.0888	0.2442	0.2441

These results show that potassium iodide, ferrous ammonium sulphate, thallous chloride, arsenious oxide and potassium antimonyl tartrate can be potentiometrically determined by using potassium chlorate as the titrating agent.

The authors thank the Khalsa College authorities for a research grant.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
KHALSA COLLEGE,
AMRITSAR.

Received December 5, 1938.